

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

INFO-COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AS A COMPONENT OF THE NOOSPHERE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyses the role and significance of the system of info-communication technologies in the structure of the noosphere. The article substantiates the importance of this system as the most important factor in the development of human civilisation at the present stage. The formation of the system of info-communication technologies is considered as a necessary and natural stage in the development of the noosphere. It is concluded that info-communication technologies are the most dynamic, truly innovative and evolving factor, which, as a result, acquires a system-forming significance for modern society.

Keywords: noosphere, civilization, information society, infocommunication technologies, system-forming factor.

The emergence and functioning of the information society, the core of which is the system of info-communication technologies, has become an objective reality of the 21st century. Various aspects of these phenomena are constantly described in modern literature. However, in our opinion, not enough attention is paid to their study as a necessary and natural stage in the evolution of both human society and planet Earth as a whole. Meanwhile, the use of available scientific approaches to the study of phenomena of this type would allow a deeper understanding of the specifics of this period of planetary evolution. One of the theories forming the methodological basis for the analysis of these problems is undoubtedly the doctrine of Academician N.I. Vernadsky about noosphere.

V.I. Vernadsky's system of ideas about noosphere as a new planetary shell arising as a result of conscious (and in this sense reasonable) human activity is one of those scientific theories, the meaning and significance of which are not lost or diminished with time. Although the term "noosphere" was introduced into scientific circulation by French scientists Edouard Leroy and Teilhard de Chardin, it was V.I. Vernadsky who created a consistent and holistic scientific theory that reveals the conditions and regularities of the emergence and development of this special stage of evolution of the planet Earth

In our opinion, information and communication technologies have turned at the present stage into one of the most important components of the noosphere as a planetary shell. In order to correctly analyse their role and significance in this capacity, it is necessary to fix at least two substantial interpretations of the concept "noosphere" in the works of V.I. Vernadsky.

Firstly, he interpreted the noosphere as a certain stage in the planetary development of the Earth. The scientist emphasised on the natural, necessary for the Earth's further existence process of noosphere emergence as a universal planetary shell, based on the geochemical principle of "growth of geochemical energy"

put forward by him. He emphasised that the emergence of the noosphere as part of the biosphere is a natural phenomenon, much deeper and more powerful in its basis than the entire previous human history.

Secondly, the noosphere was also interpreted as a stage of reasonable transformation of the environment in which man lives. V.I. Vernadsky emphasised that the presence of consciousness as a necessary component of human subject-transformative activity does not automatically mean that this activity is carried out reasonably in the true sense of the word. Human activity can lead to undesirable, even dangerous for him/herself consequences. Therefore, with the emergence of the noosphere, when human capabilities are comparable with the actions of natural forces, it is absolutely necessary to develop the level of mankind's knowledge of the laws of the surrounding world and realise the goals of its own evolution in unity with the evolution of the rest of the planet.

Besides, the fact of the noosphere emergence as a fundamentally new planetary shell also means a known separation of man from the processes of the Earth's evolution proper. It is at this stage that mankind is able to overcome the Earth's gravity and leave the limits of its environment of origin. In other words, human activity turns into a factor not only of terrestrial but also of cosmic evolution. Under such conditions, the importance of human rationality in the broadest sense of the word increases manifold. And in this sense, the noosphere (exactly as a sphere of reason, as a reasonably organised sphere of humanity's habitation) should be understood not only as one of the planetary shells and a stage of earth evolution, but also as a goal of the future development of mankind. And this goal can be achieved on condition of understanding the human being not as a "purely" planetary, terrestrial factor, but as a force that goes beyond the limits of a separate planet and becomes significant for the whole Universe in infinite time.

In his works, V.I. Vernadsky systematised quite comprehensively the factors that are required for the formation and successful functioning and development of the noosphere. Let us try to briefly analyse those of them, which are directly related to the functioning of the system of information and communication technologies - "sharp transformation of means of communication and information exchange" and "freedom of scientific thought and scientific search from the pressure of religious, philosophical and political constructions" [1].

The emergence at the end of the twentieth century and functioning in modern conditions of the information society clearly demonstrates the importance of info-communication technologies as its system-forming element. The latter act as one of the most important factors of sustainable existence and further development of human civilisation. (In this regard, it is impossible not to emphasise the depth of scientific foresight of V.I. Vernadsky, who not only put this factor in the second place in terms of importance, but also noted the impossibility of realising the first most important factor without it - "human settlement of the entire planet").

To study the real significance of information and communication technologies, it is necessary to consider their functioning in the structure of the noosphere as a sufficiently formed planetary shell. Once emerged, the noosphere begins to evolve as an independent system. Its inherent laws lead to the emergence and subsequent selection of such mechanisms, the objective need for which arises at a certain stage of development. Moreover, the most significant mechanisms appear most often in those structural elements of the noosphere that are essential for it, i.e. related, first of all, to the functioning of "reason and knowledge". The emergence of such innovative in nature elements stimulates the progress of human society on a planetary scale not only indirectly. They are directly included in the evolutionary development of the entire Earth and become one of the most important internal components of this process. As a result of their impact, existing structures are also changing. These components turn out after some time to be independent "branches of evolution", the development of which is in many respects similar to the reproduction and evolution of living organisms, when the emergence of some new factor, seemingly not too significant initially, may later give rise to fundamentally new directions. Vernadsky also drew attention to this regularity, noting that "...the course of scientific thought, for example, in the creation of machines... is absolutely similar to the course of reproduction of organisms." [2]. It can be concluded that the noosphere to ensure continuous sustainable functioning develops internal mechanisms of self-regulation and self-preservation.

This general theoretical position is perfectly illustrated by the example of the emergence and development of the global telecommunication computer network Internet.

Based on rather narrow and private needs (in this case, the need of the US Department of Defense for a secure data transmission system), a certain local system is created. Gradually it develops and slightly goes beyond the segment of the world civilisation initially assigned to it. However, its own laws of functioning give

rise to a number of new elements, which in the end fundamentally change the meaning of this system and make it global in importance. At the same time, the creators of these elements initially do not even assume such a possibility.

This component of the noosphere, which has become global in scale and degree of influence on the entire human civilisation, emerges precisely when the need for it is formed. At the same time, almost instantly (on the scale of human history), information and communication technologies cease to be an innovative phenomenon that is not very clear beyond a narrow circle of specialists. Suffice it to note that the International Telecommunication Union developed an index of information and communication technology development by country in 2007 and has been presenting it annually since then. In other words, the quantitative parameters of these processes have become a standard element of statistics along with others. Therefore, we can say with certainty that within ten to fifteen years, these technologies have turned from a specific element of the scientific and military production sphere into a component of everyday life for the majority of the world's population.

As a result, we can conclude that within the noosphere, as a realisation of its internal regularities, there appears a component that objectively creates an opportunity to organise management on a planetary scale, to regulate processes within the entire Earth. At the same time, this element itself quickly shows that for its full-fledged functioning it also requires management mechanisms corresponding in scale and authority. Thus, the gradual maturation of global problems within the noosphere quickly enough generates (on the basis of realisation of its own internal laws inherent to it) the mechanism enabling their resolution. And once formed, this mechanism itself in its turn requires global instruments corresponding to it in scale and capabilities, clearly demonstrating their objective necessity. All this again stimulates further development of the processes of planetary evolution. And, according to academician N.N. Moiseev, we should already talk about the "co-evolution" of man and the Earth [3].

We can say that at present the information society as a new stage in the development of mankind (and noosphere) has entered the next stage - the system of information and communication (or info-communication) technologies as a necessary, "actually cognitive and reasonable" structural component of modern civilisation has been formed. They represent a global-scale system of receiving (production), processing, storage, transmission, distribution, exchange and consumption (use) of information. And it is gradually beginning to show qualities that were not observed in the artificial systems previously created by mankind.

Firstly, the emergence of the system of information and communication technologies is a necessary and natural stage in the development of the noosphere. The new "reasonable" shell of the Earth objectively required an all-encompassing system that would fulfil the function of a carrier of universal knowledge.

Without the information and communication technologies formed at the present stage, the noosphere cannot function holistically. As the noosphere itself genetically follows from the development of the biosphere, so the sphere of info-communication technologies logically completes the formation of the noosphere. With the emergence of the sphere of info-communication technologies, the "noos (mind)" component is finally formed as a structural element of the noosphere, as a certain "nervous system" of the entire human civilisation. It begins to really function not only as a set of "personalised minds". Info-communication technologies allow each individual, regardless of location, time, level of education, etc., to directly, actively, in real-time mode to be included in the universal planetary thought process not only potentially, but actually. (Obviously, when implementing this process, not all results are indisputably positive. There are also negative sides.) A truly generalised mind emerges, simultaneously covering the entire surface of the Earth, simultaneously involving hundreds of millions and billions of people in its functioning. It becomes a truly "planetary sphere" in its scale, in the levels of presence (from the lithosphere to the cosmos), in the depth of influence on the processes occurring on the Earth, and in the speed of transmission of these influences.

Secondly, information and communication technologies are, in our opinion, the most dynamic component of the noosphere in comparison with the rest. Just as the functioning of human society itself (compared to other components of nature) is the least limited by external factors, so human mind, its functioning is the fastest, the most dynamic, the least limited by external factors. Thus, the sphere of info-communication technologies, capable of independently regulating, changing, pushing back the technical and concrete-historical cognitive frameworks that restrain it, is fundamentally more dynamic in its essence than those systems that depend primarily on external factors.

Thirdly, information and communication technologies are also a truly innovative component of the noosphere in their essence. The human mind is most fully realised precisely when mastering the new, previously unknown. And the system of info-communication

technologies also has as a reference point of its development the constant mastering of new knowledge. At the same time, it creates unprecedented opportunities and conditions for such activity. As a result, the cognitive capabilities of mankind rise to a qualitatively new level, which, in its turn, makes the noosphere even more "reasonable".

Fourthly, the system of information technologies is an evolving element of the noosphere. The regularities that the noosphere possesses lead to the emergence of new mechanisms necessary for its functioning at a certain stage. Processes similar in many respects to evolutionary selection in living nature are observed. In this sense, info-communication technologies as the "nervous system" of the noosphere act, first of all, as an active regulator of the ongoing transformations. In addition, they also fulfil the function of initiating relevant transformations in all spheres of human society.

Thus, infocommunication technologies in modern conditions increasingly demonstrate their intrinsic system-forming properties and actively extend them to other structural components of human society. At the present stage of human civilisation functioning, the system of these technologies ceases to be an auxiliary structure (albeit a very important one) that provides mere information transfer within the noosphere. By the beginning of the XXI century, information and communication technologies have reached such a level of development that they themselves begin to set new parameters of the systemic organisation of other structural components of human civilisation (economic, social, political, spiritual). As a result, these elements are transformed in accordance with the norms, procedures and rules of construction, which are determined by the info-communication sphere.

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